

ARTICLE

School-Based Feeding Program Implementation and Its Influence on Learners' Academic Performance

Glessie D. Lacbayen ¹

¹Toweville Elementary School
glessie.lacbayen@deped.gov.ph

Citation

Lacbayen, G. D. (2024). School-based feeding program implementation and its influence on learners' academic performance. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Econometrics*, 1(1), 1-10.

Submitted: 25-Aug, 2024

Accepted: 26-Sep, 2024

Published: 25-Oct, 2025

Vol. 1, No. 1, 2024.

 [10.62762/JTAE.2024.000000](https://doi.org/10.62762/JTAE.2024.000000)

*Corresponding author:

Glessie D. Lacbayen

glessie.lacbayen@deped.gov.ph

Copyright © 2024 by author(s) and Scientific Research Publishing Inc. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Abstract

This study was conducted to assess the influence of school feeding programs on learners' academic performance in public elementary schools of District 2, Division of San Jose del Monte, Bulacan. The descriptive correlational research design was used for this study. This study was qualitative. A questionnaire was administered to capture the influence of 77 respondents in three (3) public elementary schools in District 2. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics. The results revealed that school feeding programs significantly influenced learners' academic performance. The analysis has indicated that the school feeding program had increased the general weighted average of learners. The study recommends that the in-school feeding program should be continued. However, stakeholders need to strengthen the monitoring and involvement of the fruit and vegetable inclusions and other parameters.

Keywords: school-based feeding program, implementation, academic performance, Department of Education.

Introduction

Education has been an utmost priority in developing countries. One of the problems rooted in producing quality education while the people suffer from malnutrition and nutrient deficiency. This stigma is not a novelty because the country has dense nutrients and health problems. Gladly, many government and nongovernment organizations have lent hands to numerous feeding projects to minimize pupils' hunger and nutritional deprivation since this problem has not been eradicated for decades.

The Department of Education (2020) will maintain its commitment to providing good nutrition to learners despite of the crisis the country is facing. It declared continuance of its School-Based Feeding Program (SBFP) for the school year 2020-2021 to mitigate, if not solve, hunger and consequently motivate learners to continue their studies to improve their nutritional status and provide good nutrition for their growth and development.

It should be a priority for the government to guarantee food and nutritional security for its population. Keeley, et.al (2019) there are more than 802 million people worldwide face food insecurity. Their data showed that at least one in three children lacks the essential food for their health and physical development. The same situation or challenge happens in the Philippines. We should never forget that learners have the right to access quality and sufficient food. Good nutrition will help the child's intellectual and physical development, which accelerates as they grow. This is the very reason SBFP is an effective program.

Good nutrition is an armor to attain academic achievement. It would be a struggle for malnourished learners to have an excellent academic record because balanced nutrition is vital for endurance, physical growth, cognitive development, and productivity (Opoola et al., 2016). Additionally, malnutrition affects the learners' ability to learn, resulting in their low performance in school because of their empty stomachs. It is conceivable that stunted learners were more likely to drop out of school and would instead remain in the community (Mazengia and Biks, 2018).

Nutritious food packs, like the Department of Education's rations to the learners during the pandemic times, are vital in continuing nourishing children despite the crisis. This intervention became more helpful during the surge of COVID 19 because the parents lost their jobs which were supposed to push parents to stop their children from studying. It was said in the article of Cupertino et al. (2022) that Brazil is trying to seek the main criteria in preparing school menus: habits, food culture, acceptance; nutritional characteristics; food availability, management, and execution.

Since this researcher involved herself in the feeding programs for learners conducted in her school, the facts stated above gave her the confidence to conduct her research to identify and relate the school-based feeding program to their academic performance. Furthermore, the researcher seeks to determine more significant factors to help improve learners' academic performance.

Statement of the Problem

The general problem of this study is how may the influence of school-based feeding program implementation on learners' academic performance be determined?". Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of School-Based Feeding Program in terms of:
 - 1.1. delivery and pick up on drop off points;
 - 1.2. food safety;
 - 1.3. health and safety protocols?
2. How may the learners' academic performance be determined in terms of their

general weighted average?"

3. Does the extent of implementation of the school-based feeding program exert significant influence on learners' academic performance?
4. What management implications may be drawn from the findings of the study?

Hypothesis

In this study the following null hypothesis was tested: The extent of implementation of the school-based feeding program does not significantly influence the learners' academic performance.

Methodology

In this study, a descriptive correlational design was employed. Descriptive correlational research designs are studies that describe the variables and the relationship that occur naturally between and among them (Sousa et al., 2007). The correlational research design determines the prevalence and relationships among variables and forecasts events from current data and knowledge (Curtis et al., 2016). This study was conducted on the 77 teachers and 208 learners from the three (3) big schools of District 2, San Jose del Monte, Bulacan, respectively: Goldenville Elementary School, Minuyan Elementary School, and Towerville Elementary School.

This used the systematic random sampling technique and used the adopted questionnaire from the monitoring tool used in CALABARZON crafted by Neil Evangelista in 2021, where it was created and used for Region IV-A monitoring of the SBFP. Each item was answered using 4 scales and corresponding verbal description: 4 –Fully Implemented, 3 – Moderately Implemented, 2- Somewhat Implemented, and 1 – Not Implemented. The researcher sent the link for the online survey via Google form to the feeding coordinators of the three (3) schools. The responses in this monitoring tool were handled responsibly and will not be used to assess the school's performance. The following statistical treatments were used to interpret the data's results. The gathered data were encoded, analyzed, and interpreted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26. Descriptive statistics such as frequency and weighted mean were used to describe the extent of implementation of SBFP in terms of delivery and pick up on drop-off points, food safety, and health and safety protocols. They were measured using the following Likert Scale, which was interpreted using the numerical value with the corresponding equivalent. To describe the profile of learners in terms of their general weighted average, mean and standard deviation were computed. To determine the significant relationship between the extent of implementation of the School-Based Feeding Program and academic performance of the learners, paired sample t test was employed at 0.05 level of significance.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. *Frequency and mean distribution of responses on the extent of implementation of school-based feeding program*

INDICATORS	Frequency	Average Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	1	2	3	4
A. DELIVERY AND PICK UP ON DROP OFF POINTS (MILK AND NFP)							
Delivered by supplier on scheduled and agreed time	0 1 7 69	3.88	Fully Implemented				drop off points on

Picked-up by schools delivery on drop off points	0 1 7 69	3.88	Fully Implemented immediately after
---	----------	------	-------------------------------------

B. FOOD SAFETY

B.1 For Milk

Delivered milk were	0 1 5 71	3.91	Fully Implemented frozen/chilled
---------------------	----------	------	----------------------------------

Delivered milk were	0 1 4 72	3.92	Fully Implemented placed in coolers with ice
---------------------	----------	------	--

Delivered milk were	1 1 8 67	3.83	Fully Implemented with 7 days shelf life
---------------------	----------	------	--

B.2 For Nutritious Food Products (for Fortified Bread and Pastries)

Delivered Nutritious Food Product were placed in sealed container or bag to maintain freshness, quality and safety	1 0 8 68	3.86	Fully Implemented
---	----------	------	-------------------

INDICATORS	Frequency	Average Mean	Descriptive Equivalent	1	2	3	4
------------	-----------	--------------	------------------------	---	---	---	---

Date of Production or Consume Before date were indicated	1 0 6 70	3.92	Fully Implemented				
---	----------	------	-------------------	--	--	--	--

NFP were placed in a delivery to avoid touching surfaces and maintain safety	1 0 7 69	3.87	Fully Implemented try or container upon				
---	----------	------	---	--	--	--	--

B.3 FOOD SAFETY IN THE DISPATCHING AREA

Dispatching area was	1 0 9 67	3.84	Fully Implemented well-lit
----------------------	----------	------	----------------------------

Dispatching area was	1 0 7 69	3.87	Fully Implemented pest free
----------------------	----------	------	-----------------------------

Dispatching area was	1 0 6 70	3.88	Fully Implemented clean
----------------------	----------	------	-------------------------

B.4 OBSERVING OF PROPER HYGIENE FOR FOOD SAFETY

Washing of hands	1 0 6 70	3.88	Fully Implemented were observed
------------------	----------	------	---------------------------------

Wearing of disposable	1 0 7 69	3.87	Fully Implemented plastic gloves
-----------------------	----------	------	----------------------------------

Wearing of hairnet	1 1 8 67	3.83	Fully Implemented was evident
--------------------	----------	------	-------------------------------

Wearing of apron	1 0 7 69	3.87	Fully Implemented was evident
------------------	----------	------	-------------------------------

C. HEALTH AND SAFETY PROTOCOL

Conducted thermo- the premises	0 1 9 67	3.86	Fully Implemented scanning upon entering
Accepted delivery	1 0 7 69	3.87	Fully Implemented of goods spaces and area
Available sanitizing	1 0 9 67	3.84	Fully Implemented foot bath was evident
Available alcohol and evident	1 0 9 67	3.84	Fully Implemented hand sanitizers were
Wearing of face mask	1 0 3 73	3.92	Fully Implemented was observed
INDICATORS	Frequency	Average Mean	Descriptive Equivalent 1 2 3 4
Physical distancing	1 0 7 69	3.87	Fully Implemented was observed
Wearing of face shield	1 0 5 71	3.90	Fully Implemented was observed
Dispatching area was	1 0 7 69	3.87	Fully Implemented properly ventilated
	Overall Mean	3.88	Fully Implemented

The data shows that the delivery and pick-up on drop-off points were “fully implemented.” It claims that the milk and food packs were delivered by a supplier at a scheduled time and immediately picked up by schools with an average mean of 3.88. As for monitoring food safety for the milk, nutritious food products, proper hygiene in handling food, and dispatching areas were also “fully implemented,”

Table 2. Profile of learners in terms of their general weighted average

School	N	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal description
A	59	82.64	2.98	Satisfactory
B	47	83.66	3.39	Satisfactory
C	102	84.10	2.53	Satisfactory
Overall mean		83.47	2.97	Satisfactory

It can be gleaned from the data that the learners were all performing well academically because the means ranged from 82.64-84.10. Satisfactory academic performance will lead

learners to admission opportunities in their next level of education, so that the other way will happen for poor academic performance. However, Saleh et al. (2018) clarified that many determinates are affecting academic performance that needs to be considered to boost the cognitive ability of learners.

Table 3 *Influence of school-based feeding program on learners' academic performance*

School	Mean	Standard deviation	Computed value	Critical value	Decision	Interpretation
A	80.62	4.06	5.39	2.00	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant
	82.64	2.98				
B	81.70	3.86	3.39	2.01	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant
	83.66	2.79				
C	81.68	3.03	7.50	1.98	Reject the null hypothesis	Significant
	84.10	2.53				

It can be observed in this data that before the school feeding program, the learners gained the mean of 80.62 and had a standard deviation of 4.06, while after the conduct, the mean average of students increased to 82.64 with a standard deviation of 2.98 and it has a computed value of 5.39 with the critical value of 2.00 interpreted as "significant." Since the computed value is greater than the critical value, the null hypothesis was rejected; therefore, school feeding programs significantly influence learners' academic performance.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The implementation of the school-based feeding program was found to be successfully monitored and follows guidelines, as can be deemed from the data where all indicators were fully implemented. Learners in the three (3) big schools were found to have a "satisfactory" academic performance.
2. Feeding program is one factor that positively affects the learners' academic performance. Nutritious food packs given to learners encourage them to participate in school activities, as can be gleaned from the data that the learners from the three (3)

schools had improved their grades from SY 2019-2020 compared to their current general weighted average on SY 2020-2021 were the nutritious food packs had been implemented.

Recommendations

In light of the previous significant findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. School heads may continue their school feeding program because of its great help to learners who are encouraged to attend school.
2. It would be more effective if teachers would strengthen the monitoring to see that the recipient herself eats the food packs.
3. Parents may strengthen their support for learners' academic to strive harder. In this new normal, they should participate in their roles in their child's studies, like in getting the modules.
4. Learners should eat all the inclusions in the food packs to take all the nutrients needed for their mental and health development. They should possess a positive mindset to maintain exemplary academic performance despite external factors.
5. For future researchers, it is suggested that they include additional parameters or variables that will gauge the success of the feeding program, not just its implementation. It would also be significant to include variables like learners' age, gender, BMI, and parents' economic status.

References

1. Aceron, A. (2019). Nutritional status and its impact on academic performance of selected Grade 8 students. *In Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1254, No. 1, p. 012013). IOP Publishing. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1254/1/012013/meta>
2. Adelman, S., Gilligan, D., Konde-Lule, J., & Alderman, H. (2019) School feeding reduces anemia prevalence in adolescent girls and other vulnerable household members in a cluster randomized controlled trial in Uganda. *The Journal of Nutrition*, 149(4), 659-666. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30926996/>
3. Alipio, M. (2020). Adjustment to college and academic performance: Insights from Filipino college freshmen in an allied health science course. <https://edarxiv.org/74ysf/>
4. Atallah, N. (2020). Exploring the impact of teachers' motivation on the academic performance of students the case of master one students at foreign languages department in the University of Biskra. http://archives.univbiskra.dz/bitstream/123456789/16129/1/Nesrine_Atallah.pdf

5. Atienza. (2021). DepEd's feeding program for SY 2021-2022 to benefit 3.1 million learners. <https://mb.com.ph/2021/07/23/depeds-feeding-program-for-schoolyear-2021-2022-to-benefit-3-1-million-learners/>
6. Aurino, E., Tranchant, J., Sekou Diallo, A., & Gelli, A. (2019) School feeding or general food distribution? Quasi-experimental evidence on the educational impacts of emergency food assistance during conflict in Mali. *The Journal of Development Studies*, 55(sup1), 7-28. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/00220388.2019.1687874>
7. Child Hope Philippines (2021) Kalyenderia: Childhope's advocacy to address food insecurity and hunger amid COVID-19. <https://childhope.org.ph/kalyenderiachildhope-feeding-program-covid-19/>
8. Cohen, J. F., Hecht, A. A., McLoughlin, G. M., Turner, L., & Schwartz, M. B. (2021). Universal school meals and associations with student participation, attendance, academic performance, diet quality, food security, and body mass index: A systematic review. *Nutrients*, 13(3), 911. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/33799780/>
9. Cupertino, A., Ginani, V., Cupertino, A. P., & Botelho, R. B. A. (2022). School feeding programs: What happens globally? *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 19(4), 2265. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35206451/>
10. Department of Education (2021). DepEd eyes 3.1M beneficiaries for school-based feeding program for the upcoming school year. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/2021/07/23/deped-eyes-3-1m-beneficiaries-for-school-based-feeding-program-for-the-upcoming-school-year/>
11. Deped Order No. 23 (2020). Operational guidelines on the implementation of the school based feeding program for school year 2020-2021. https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/09/DO_s2020_023.pdf
12. Desalegn et al (2021). The effect of school feeding programme on class absenteeism and academic performance of schoolchildren in Southern Ethiopia: a prospective cohort study. <https://www.cambridge.org/core/journals/public-health-nutrition/article/effectof-school-feeding-programme-on-classabsenteeism-and-academicperformance-ofschoolchildren-insouthern-ethiopiaapropective-cohortstudy/8B2016299563F061EF5031511ABDE6B1>
13. Estandarte. (2021). P6.4 billion allocated to feed undernourished kids in public schools. <https://www.smartparenting.com.ph/life/news/school-based-feedingprogram-deped-2021-2022-a2116-20210909>
14. Evangelista, N. (2021). School-based feeding program monitoring tool. Region IV-A, Calabarzon. <https://depedcalabarzon.ph/wp-content/uploads/2021/03/RM-NO-125-S.-2021.pdf>
15. Food and Agriculture Organization (2019). Nutrition guidelines and standards for school meals: a report from 33 low and middle-income countries. https://linkscommunity.org/assets/PDFs/fao_nutrition-guidelines-andstandards-for-school-meals_a-report-from-33-low-and-middle-incomecountries.pdf
16. Horca, J. S. (2021). School based feeding program: It's impact on the academic performance of severely wasted pupils of Southville Elementary School S.Y. 2015-2016. Academia. https://www.academia.edu/29404390/School_Based
17. Feeding_Program_It_s_Impact_on_the_Academic_Performance_of_Severely_Wasted_Pupils_of_Southville_Elementary_School_S_Y_2015_2016

18. De Dieu, J. (2022). Effect school feeding programme on learners' academic performance. A case of Gsrwakirari and Gskayeyo in Kivuruga Sector of District Gakenke, Rwanda (2015-2019). http://www.voiceofresearch.org/Doc/Mar-2022/Mar-2022_7.pdf
19. Keeley, B., Little, C., & Zuehlke, E. (2019). The state of the world's children 2019: Children, food and nutrition--growing well in a changing world. *UNICEF*.
<https://www.unicef.org/reports/state-of-worlds-children-2019>
20. Kwatubana, S., & Molaodi, V. T. (2021). Ensuring the continuation of school feeding programmes during COVID-19 pandemic: A case of "new normal" management. *Bulgarian Comparative Education Society*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED614001.pdf>
21. Liburd, L.C. (2019). After the bell rings: Looking beyond the classroom to reduce inequalities in educational achievement and health outcomes. *J Public Health Manag Pract*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30789595/>
22. Lu, M. J. M., & Dacal, R. L. (2020). Implementation of school-based feeding program and its effect on the physical growth and academic performance. *Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3(2). <https://asianjournal.org/online/index.php/ajms/article/view/300>
23. Maijo, S. N. (2019). Impact of school feeding programme on learners' academic performance in Mlunduzi Luward, Tanzania. *International journal of educational studies*, 5(3), 125-130. <https://esciencepress.net/journals/index.php/IJES/article/view/2667>
24. McCarthy. (2021). 5 ways school meals benefit children and transform communities. https://www.globalcitizen.org/en/content/school-meals-benefits-studentswfp/?gclid=EAIaIQobChMItNXm76TTwIVAbawCh3TjgaYEAAYASAAEgJRPvD_BwE
25. National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine. (2019). Promoting positive adolescent health behaviors and outcomes: Thriving in the 21st century. *Washington, DC: The National Academies Press*. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/32182004/>
26. National Nutrition Council Region 8. (2022). Merida, Leyte implements Schoolbased Feeding Program. https://www.nnc.gov.ph/regionaloffices/visayas/regio_____n-viii-eastern-visayas/7293-merida-leyte-implements-school-based-feedingprogram
27. Obligado (2019). Impact of school-based feeding program on the academic performance and nutritional status of Grade 4 pupils. <https://ojs.aaresearchindex.com/index.php/AAJMRA/article/view/6152>
28. Reuter, P. R., Forster, B. L., & Brister, S. R. (2021). The influence of eating habits on the academic performance of university students. *Journal of American*
29. *College Health*, 69(8), 921-927. https://www.fgcu.edu/mariebcollege/rehabilitationosciences/files/The_influence_of_eating_habits_on_the_academic_performance_of_university_students_2020.pdf
30. Shrestha, R., Schreinemachers, P., Nyangmi, M., Sah, M., Phuong, J., & Manandhar, S. (2020) Home-grown school feeding: Assessment of a pilot program in Nepal. *BMC Public Health*, 20(1), 28. <https://bmcpublikealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12889-019-8143-9>
31. Shikongo, L. (2021). Home-grown school feeding program set to improve nutrition whilst boosting the local economy. <https://www.wfp.org/news/home-growschool-feeding-programme-set-improve->

nutrition-whilst-boosting-

32. Soriano. (2020). School-based feeding program S.Y. 2020-2021. <http://marcelogreenes.depedparanaquecity.com/uncategorized/brigada-eskwela/>
33. Tadalán, C. A. (2021). Coronavirus pandemic highlights failures of Philippine education. *BusinessWorld*. *Business World*. <https://www.bworldonline.com/coronavirus-pandemic-highlights-failures-of-philippine-education>.
34. Wang, D., & Fawzi, W. W. (2020). Impacts of school feeding on educational and health outcomes of school-age children and adolescents in low-and middleincome countries: Protocol for a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Christian perspectives in education*. <http://digitalcommons.liberty.edu/cpe/vol5/iss1/1>.
35. World Food Programme (2019). State of school feeding worldwide. <https://www.wfp.org/publications/2019-wfp-school-feeding-infographic>